

New combinations in Vietnamese Ferns

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Article Details: Received: 2025-01-21 | Accepted: 2025-05-01 | Available online: 2025-05-05

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Abstract: Three new combinations are proposed here in the Ferns of Vietnam, one in Marattiaceae and two in Polypodiaceae.

Keywords: *Angiopteris*, Endemic, *Leptochilus*, Marattiaceae, Polypodiaceae, *Selliguea*

Introduction

The genus *Angiopteris* Hoffm. (Marattiaceae) consists of about 60 species, distributed in tropical and subtropical Asia to Pacific, and West Indian Ocean (POWO, 2025). In Vietnam, the genus is represented by about 13 species, namely *A. annamensis* C.Chr. & Tardieu, *A. cadierei* (C.Chr. & Tardieu) R.Kr.Singh & V.K.Rawat, *A. caudatiformis* Hieron., *A. cochinchinensis* de Vriese, *A. confertinervia* Ching ex C.Chr. & Tardieu, *A. dianyuicola* Z.R.He & W.M.Chu, *A. hokouensis* Ching, *A. indica* Desv., *A. palmiformis* (Cav.) C.Chr., *A. somae* (Hayata) Makino & Nemoto, *A. tamdaoensis* (Hayata) J.Y.Xiang & T.Wang, *A. tonkinensis* (Hayata) J.M.Camus and *A. yunnanensis* Hieron., of which *A. cadierei* is endemic (POWO, 2025). However, the name *Archangiopteris cadierei* C.Chr. & Tardieu needs to be transferred to the genus *Angiopteris*, because in current circumscription *Archangiopteris* Christ & Giesenh. is synonymous to *Angiopteris* (Wang et al., 2020). Therefore, a new combination is proposed here for *Archangiopteris cadierei* under the genus *Angiopteris* as *A. cadierei* (C.Chr. & Tardieu) R.Kr.Singh & V.K.Rawat.

The genus *Leptochilus* Kaulf. (Polypodiaceae) is represented by about 48 species, distributed in tropical and subtropical Asia to Pacific (POWO, 2025). In Vietnam, the genus consists of about 28 species, namely *L. axillaris* (Cav.) Kaulf., *L. cantoniensis* (Baker) Ching, *L. chilangensis* (V.N.Tu) Liang

Zhang & Li Bing Zhang, *L. chingii* Liang Zhang & Li Bing Zhang, *L. daklakensis* Liang Zhang, X.M.Zhou, T.T.Luong & Li Bing Zhang, *L. decurrens* Blume, *L. digitatus* (Baker) Noot., *L. ellipticus* (Thunb.) Noot., *L. hemionitideus* (C.Presl) Noot., *L. henryi* (Baker) X.C.Zhang, *L. heterophyllus* (S.K.Wu & L.K.Phan) R.Kr.Singh & V.K.Rawat, *L. lanceolatus* Fée, *L. locii* Liang Zhang, N.T.Lu & Li Bing Zhang, *L. longissimus* (Blume) L.Y.Kuo, *L. minor* Fée, *L. morsei* (Ching) Fraser-Jenk., *L. neolongipes* Liang Zhang, X.M.Zhou, T.T.Luong & Li Bing Zhang, *L. oblongus* Li Bing Zhang, Liang Zhang & N.T.Lu, *L. ornithopus* T.Fujiw. & B.H.Quang, *L. ovatus* Copel., *L. pedunculatus* (Hook. & Grev.) Fraser-Jenk., *L. pothifolius* (Buch.-Ham. ex D.Don) Fraser-Jenk., *L. pteropus* (Blume) Fraser-Jenk., *L. saxicola* (H.G.Zhou & Hua Li) Liang Zhang & Li Bing Zhang, *L. × shintenensis* (Hayata) Nakaike, *L. sinovietnamica* Liang Zhang, N.T.Lu & Li Bing Zhang, *L. vietnamensis* Liang Zhang, N.T.Lu & Li Bing Zhang and *L. wrightii* (Hook.) X.C.Zhang, of which *L. chilangensis* (V.N.Tu) Liang Zhang & Li Bing Zhang, *L. chingii* Liang Zhang & Li Bing Zhang, *L. daklakensis* Liang Zhang, X.M.Zhou, T.T.Luong & Li Bing Zhang, *L. heterophyllus* (S.K.Wu & L.K.Phan) R.Kr.Singh & V.K.Rawat, *L. locii* Liang Zhang, N.T.Lu & Li Bing Zhang, *L. neolongipes* Liang Zhang, X.M.Zhou, T.T.Luong & Li Bing Zhang, *L. oblongus* Li Bing Zhang, Liang Zhang & N.T.Lu, *L. ornithopus* T.Fujiw. & B.H.Quang and *L. vietnamensis* Liang Zhang, N.T.Lu & Li Bing Zhang are endemic (POWO, 2025). However, the name *Kontumia heterophylla* S.K.Wu & L.K.Phan needs to be transferred to the genus *Leptochilus*, because in current circumscription *Kontumia* S.K.Wu & L.K.Phan is synonymous to *Leptochilus* (Kim et al., 2012; Wei & Zhang, 2022). Therefore, a new combination is proposed here for *Kontumia heterophylla* under the genus *Leptochilus* as *L. heterophyllus* (S.K.Wu & L.K.Phan) R.Kr.Singh & V.K.Rawat.

The genus *Selliguea* Bory (Polypodiaceae) consists of about 125 species, distributed in tropical and subtropical Asia to Pacific (POWO, 2025; Singh & Rawat, 2024). In Vietnam, the genus is represented by about 14 species, namely *S. amplexifolia* (Christ) Christenh., *S. capitellata* (Wall.) X.C.Zhang & L.J.He, *S. cruciformis* (Ching) Fraser-Jenk., *S. dareiformis* (Hook.) X.C.Zhang & L.J.He, *S. enervis* (Cav.) Ching, *S. griffithiana* (Hook.) Fraser-Jenk., *S. lateritia* (Baker) Hovenkamp, *S. lehmannii* (Mett.) Christenh., *S. moulmeinensis* (Bedd.) X.C.Zhang & L.J.He, *S. nigrovenia* (Christ) S.G.Lu, Hovenkamp & M.G.Gilbert, *S. oxyloba* (Wall. ex Kunze) Fraser-Jenk., *S. rhynchophylla* (Hook.) Fraser-Jenk., *S. tamdaoensis* (V.N.Tu) R.Kr.Singh & V.K.Rawat and *S. triloba* (Houtt.) M.G.Price, of which *S. tamdaoensis* is endemic (POWO, 2025). However, the name *Crypsinus tamdaoensis* V.N.Tu needs to be transferred to the genus *Selliguea*, because in current circumscription *Crypsinus* C.Presl is synonymous to *Selliguea* (Wei & Zhang, 2022). Therefore, a new combination is proposed here for *Crypsinus tamdaoensis* under the genus *Selliguea* as *S. tamdaoensis* (V.N.Tu) R.Kr.Singh & V.K.Rawat.

New combinations

Marattiaceae

Angiopteris cadierei (C.Chr. & Tardieu) R.Kr.Singh & V.K.Rawat, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Archangiopteris cadierei* C.Chr. & Tardieu, Notul. Syst. (Paris) 5: 5, t.1(1-2). 1935.

Figure 1: Isotype of *Archangiopteris cadieri* C. Chr. & Tardieu (BM000786650, © The Natural History Museum, London)

Figure 2: Paratype of *Kontumia heterophylla* S.K.Wu & L.K.Phan (C0367023F, © Field Museum of Natural History, Chicago)

Figure 3: Paratype of *Kontumia heterophylla* S.K.Wu & L.K.Phan (L3556698, © Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Leiden)

Figure 4: Paratype of *Kontumia heterophylla* S.K. Wu & L.K. Phan (MO5776200, © Herbarium of Missouri Botanical Garden, Saint Louis)

Figure 5: Paratype of *Kontumia heterophylla* S.K.Wu & L.K.Phan (MO04479896, © Herbarium of Missouri Botanical Garden, Saint Louis)

Holotype: Vietnam, Annam, Cua Tung, 50-100 m, 1932, *Léopold-Michel Cadière s.n.* (P); isotype BM000786650! (Figure 1),

Distribution: Endemic to Vietnam.

Polypodiaceae

Leptochilus heterophyllus (S.K.Wu & L.K.Phan) R.Kr.Singh & V.K.Rawat, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Kontumia heterophylla* S.K.Wu & L.K.Phan, *Novon* 15(1): 245, f. 1 & 2. 2005.

Holotype: Vietnam, Kon Tum province, Kon Plong district, Ngoc Tem Municipality, Mang La state forest, 14°41'41" N, 108°22'21" E, 1100 m, 9 April 2000, *Phan Kê Lôc* P-10551 (HN); isotypes KUN, LE, MO.

Paratypes: Vietnam, Kon Tum province, Kon Plong district, Hieu Municipality, Mang La forest enterprise, 14°39' N, 108°25' E, 1000–1200 m, primary evergreen broad-leaved wet forest on steep mountain slopes on sandstone and gneiss, 15 April 2000, *L. Averyanov et al.* VH-5129 [HN, F (Figure 2), L (Figure 3), LE, MO (Figure 4)]; Kon Plong district, Hieu Municipality, 14°41'48" N, 108°22'23" E, c 1250 m, 20 November 2003, *Wu et al.* WP-136 (HN, KUN, MO); Kon Plong district, Po E Municipality, first village, 14°43'16" N, 108°38'18" E, c 1200 m, logged primary closed evergreen seasonal tropical broad-leaved submontane forests on slope of mountains, 22 November 2003, S.G. *Wu et al.* WP-201 [HN, KUN, MO (Figure 5)].

Distribution: Endemic to Vietnam.

Selliguea tamdaoensis (V.N.Tu) R.Kr.Singh & V.K.Rawat, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Crypsinus tamdaoensis* V.N.Tu, *Bot. Zhurn. (Moscow & Leningrad)* 64(9): 1316. 1979.

Holotype: Vietnam, Tam Dao (not traceable).

Distribution: Endemic to Vietnam.

Acknowledgements

The authors are thankful to the Director, Botanical Survey of India, Kolkata and Head of Office, Botanical Survey of India, Arid Zone Regional Centre, Jodhpur for facilities.

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